

Workshop scenario Multi-Actor Role Playing Game

How do you align views in a MAA process?

In-person workshop

Timing: 2,5-3 hours, 8 or 12 people

Objective of the session:

- to put everybody in the position of a member of a multi-actor co-innovation proposal group;
- change perspectives by taking another actor's perspective (non-academic partners chose an academic role; academic partners get a non-academic role); and
- give people a feeling of what a multi-actor proposal development looks like

Material and resources

- [Simplified and shortened call for proposal](#)
- [Character descriptions](#) and separate A1 poster templates with the storyline and description of five characters ([Poster template Round 1](#))
- A0 poster templates to support the exchange in [Round 2](#) and [Round 3](#)
- Pink, green and yellow post its
- Enough markers for the participants
- Briefed facilitators:
 - Every mixed group is joined by one facilitator. Depending on the group size you would need more facilitators or work in larger groups.
 - One overall facilitator and timekeeper
 - Facilitators should have read the entire scenario and can use the [more detailed character descriptions](#) to support the participants in 'playing' their role.

Introduction (15 min)

The focus of the workshop is to support the participants' understanding of what it means to become involved in multi-actor project proposals. As we want to support participants to immerse themselves as quickly as possible into the different roles, we ONLY introduce what will happen in the coming hours. It is only at the end of the workshop that we can introduce the PREMIERE project and how the project can help them in their future endeavours in multi-actor settings.

Introduce the roleplaying game using the powerpoint:

- Process and workshop timeline:
3 rounds and time for reflection and discussion afterwards
- Rules of engagement

The [call for proposals](#) of for the multi-actor project the participants will work on is shortly introduced. This call for proposals is also provided in print to each of the participants.

Round 1 – Getting into the role: identifying needs, interests, red lines (30 mins)

The group is divided over four roles of the simulated multi-actor roleplaying game. In the first round participants will sit together with others who will play the same character in the rest of the workshop. Depending on the group size, they will sit together with 2 or 3 people. The objective is that they help each other to better understand who their character is and how they will play them in the next rounds of the workshop. Each group can be joined by a facilitator to help them crawl into the skin of the character or you can work with ‘floating facilitators’ who check in occasionally on how the group is doing.

[Participants will have a template to map:](#)

- The interest this character has in the project proposal – WHY does this character want to be part of the proposal?
- What would this character definitely NOT want to do, where are the red lines? What would this character not do well?
- What type of activity would this character like to do, taking into account the call for proposals? What do you think they would be good at?

Participants will first brainstorm on these three questions and write down everything they come up with. This way, they are putting ‘flesh’ on the bones of their character.

When there are five minutes left in this round, the facilitators will instruct the participants to choose for themselves what is the key interest of their character, the key red line and the most important activity. The participants that were working on the same character do not necessarily have the same 3 points to take along. They can choose individually what they find the most essential interests, activities and red lines for their characters.

- ⇒ The final result of this round is that each participant has for their character:
 1. A **GREEN** sticky note with the key interest they HAVE to have in the proposal
 2. A **YELLOW** sticky note with the one activity that builds on their key interest
 3. A **PINK** sticky note with the most prominent red line for their character.
- ⇒ Each participant will take these three sticky notes with them to their new groups in the next Round.

Round 2 – Mixing the groups: Finding out the different stances of the five different characters (30 min)

The participants will now move to the mixed, multi-actor groups. In each group there will be 1 participant representing each character (this can also be done in tandem, i.e. two people taking up the role of one character, depending on the group size).

When the 4 participants come together in their mixed groups, the facilitator will do a ‘tour de table’. Each participant is invited to introduce themselves as their character and to share their key **INTEREST** and **RED LINE**. They can put the according sticky note under the right heading in the [poster template](#).

The facilitator in each group will guide them through the following phases:

1. For the **interests**:
 - Which similarities do you see between your group's key interests?
 - Which differences are there?
 - Where do you see possible synergies?
2. For the **red lines**:
 - How do they relate to each other, is there any room for negotiation?
 - Do you think your character could agree with the red lines of others?
 - Where do you see potential conflict?

The facilitator can invite participants to share new interests and red lines for their characters based upon the inputs of the other participants.

At the end of this round, the group should have a better idea of who is in their group and with whom they think they could work together well or less well in the project. Knowing the synergies and potential sources of conflict will help them in Round 3.

Round 3 – In the mixed groups: What would the project look like? (25 min)

The facilitator of each group moves the discussion along to this phase by going to the [next poster canvas](#). Participants are asked to start developing their multi-actor project. Using the interests and red lines of the 5 characters, participants are asked to identify a coordinator amongst themselves, develop 3 work packages, including the theme, a leader, involved partners and identifying potential new partners. Finally, during the last ten minutes of this phase, a surprise requirement is introduced: they need to involve a social science and humanities perspective somewhere! How will they do this?

The overall facilitator introduces this last round of the discussion. Within the groups, the facilitator invites the participants to first put down their last **YELLOW** sticky note on the template and shortly introduce the key activity they had thought of in the beginning of the workshop and whether they think it is still relevant or whether they would be keen to change or adapt it. At this point, they can also share their interest in becoming the project coordinator.

From this introduction, the facilitator leads the discussion into the development of the 3 work packages which each need a leader. In this round we are looking to answer following key questions:

- Which themes will be worked on in each work package?
- Based upon the synergies you identified: Who would like to cooperate with who?
- Based upon the potential conflicts you identified: Who would rather not be involved in a certain work package with whom?
- Amongst you: who would be best placed to be the 'coordinator' and who will be 'work package leader'? I.e. to ensure that everyone is sufficiently involved and knows what to do by when?
- Are there any type of organisations or actors missing in your group? Which other types of partners would you need for the project? Where will you find them?

In the final five minutes, the facilitators will introduce **the surprise requirement that you need to involve a Social Science and Humanities component** and ask the participants to think about:

- Which type of social science and humanities domain would you include? (philosophy, political science, psychology, sociology, gender studies, educational science, etc.)
- Which type of actor or organisation could you contact to take this up?
- Where would you place the social sciences and humanities perspective in your work packages?

Round 4 – In the group of 25: Reflection (20 min)

The reflection phase, we move back into a plenary setting. Participants are invited to share with the group their own reflections. If you notice that your group is not open to do this in a plenary setting, you can also do this within each smaller group. However, it can also be interesting to have the groups comparing how they did and whether the process went into the same direction or somewhere completely different.

The overall facilitator introduces a first part of the reflection on the exercise itself and on your role:

- How did the group negotiation go from the perspective of your character? Did you succeed in getting your interests represented and your red lines followed?
- Would you have taken a different approach if it was up to your character?
- How close was this to your own 'real life' experience? How difficult was it for you to become your character?

In the second part of the reflection, the facilitator moves the participants back into their own reality and relates the exercise to the participants own role and experience:

- How does your own perspective relate to that of the five characters? Who are you closest to? Who are you furthest from?
- What was recognisable?
- What was completely different to your own experience?
- How was it for you to think about including the social sciences and humanities?
- Which is the main lesson or reflection that you take from this workshop?
- How will you take these lessons along?

Timing	Objective, Activity, Outcome	Guideline for facilitator	Resources
15 min Introduction	Introduce the roleplaying game using the powerpoint: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Process and workshop timeline: 3 rounds and time for reflection and discussion afterwards - Rules of engagement 	In the notes of the ppt	Guiding ppt
30 min Round 1	<p>Objective: The participants get to know the character they will represent by reading the character description and figuring out their character's interests and objectives, red lines and the activities they would like to implement in the project.</p> <p>Activity: there are as many tables as there are characters in the workshop. Participants are divided evenly over the tables. They engage in a facilitated discussion using the Character Templates.</p> <p>Outcome: Participants have prepared their own character, they now are able to represent this character in discussing what they will and will not be able to do in the project.</p>	<p>The ppt presentation is kept up as it provides the central thread throughout the workshop. The overall facilitator or timekeeper introduces each phase. After the introductions, the group's facilitator takes over.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participants are asked to sit down at one of the tables representing the different characters. Ideally, you have an overview of who is attending the workshop, so you can ensure that participants are invited to play a character as far away from their own experience as possible. • Participants get a name tag with the icon of their character and a number at the start of the session. • Once everyone is settled the facilitator introduces the character. The aim of sitting together is that the participants jointly try to understand who their character is. (0-5 min) • The facilitator runs the participants through the three big tables. Per point, the facilitator has 7 minutes to get participants ideas flowing. (5-12 min, 12-19 min, 19-26 min) • In the last 4 min, the facilitator will ask each participant to write down what, in their opinion, the most INTEREST, RED LINE and ACTIVITY is. This is the briefing note each participant will take to the 'first project proposal meeting' (round 2). This can 	<p>Simplified call for proposals (one print per participant)</p> <p>Character Template (in A1, one per group)</p> <p>Character Tags (labels, one per participant)</p> <p>Sticky notes and markers</p> <p>Pink, yellow and green post its (1 of each for each participant)</p> <p>4 numbered tables with space for 5 people (facilitator + participants)</p>

		be an exercise to undertake as a group or as individuals.	
30 min Round 2	<p>Objective: The participants get to know the other characters and their objectives and red lines. They are induced to think about who they have complementarities with and who they might fall into conflict with and why.</p> <p>Activity: The participants try to find both synergies and conflicts between the different characters using a facilitated discussion.</p> <p>Outcome: The simulated project proposal group has a clear understanding of which interests/objectives are aligned and where potential conflicts lie.</p>	<p>The ppt presentation guides the participants to their new groups. Once arrived the overall facilitator introduces the next round.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • STEP 1: Participants are invited to put their GREEN interest sticky note and their PINK red line sticky note on the general space one by one. They introduce themselves (in their character) and their one INTEREST + RED LINE while they put these down (10 min). • STEP 2: Once all the sticky notes are put down, the facilitator asks participants which similarities they see. These similarities can be both about objectives or interests which are similar, but also red lines which represent each other. Once the similarities are done, the facilitator asks to do the same for the red lines. (10 min) • STEP 3: Which similarities which can be seen as synergies? I.e. where the characters can build on each other's interests? While doing this the concerning sticky notes are moved to the box 'synergies'. Are there any differences which can result in potential conflicts? Which ones? You move the sticky notes to the box 'conflict' (10 min) • TIP: If there are sticky notes that can be both in the similarities and the differences, the facilitator quickly duplicates the sticky note. 	<p>Interest/Red Lines template</p> <p>Pink (red line) and Green (key interest) post its of the characters from the previous phase</p> <p>Extra sticky notes and markers for the facilitators</p>
25 min Round 3	<p>Objective: The participants gain insight into how they can build a multi-actor project and three work packages knowing the different perspectives of the other actors. They learn how to deal with differences and similarities</p>	<p>The overall facilitator indicates that it is time to move to the last phase of the exercise. The group facilitators switches the poster canvas and explains that now we are going to develop the project.</p>	<p>Yellow post it (Key activity)</p> <p>Extra sticky notes and markers</p>

	<p>and how to include these in project design. Finally, they get a short introduction in how to think about consortium-building by both asking them to identify ‘missing’ areas of expertise and the SSH requirement.</p> <p>Activity: Thinking collectively about three possible work packages and who to involve where and why.</p> <p>Outcomes: A coordinator of the project Three work packages with leaders and teams Identification of ‘missing partners’ Some thoughts on how to involve SSH in the project</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • STEP 1. Every participant is asked to introduce which activity they thought of in the beginning and whether they would like to be coordinator. The facilitator leads the discussions towards agreement on the coordinator and writes the name down. • STEP 2. Now that the first ideas for activities are proposed, the facilitator will help the participants develop three work packages and identify missing actors. • STEP3. During the last 10 minutes, the facilitator introduces the surprise requirement of involving SSH disciplines and talking about the possibilities of which SSH would be interesting to involve, why and where 	<p>Work packages Canvas</p>
<p>20 min Reflection</p>	<p>To wrap up the session and to collectively take time to reflect on what types of insights they have had and how they will take these along in their professional lives.</p>	<p>In this last phase, we go back to the plenary setting.</p> <p>Using the ppt and mentimeter, the overall facilitator asks the participants to reflect on their experience.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • STEP 1. In the first half of the reflection exercise, participants reflect on the exercise itself from the point of view of their character. • STEP 2. After this we move onto their personal reflections and the lessons they learnt during the workshop. • STEP 3. We highlight some key lessons (based upon previous experiences) and some take home messages. 	<p>PPT presentation</p> <p>Mentimeter or in plenary using flipcharts</p>

Shortened Call for Proposal for the PREMIERE Multi-actor Roleplay workshop

HORIZON-CL6-2024-BIODIV-02-3-two-stage: Promoting minor crops in farming systems¹

<i>Indicative budget</i>	The total indicative budget for the topic is EUR 10.00 million.
<i>Type of Action</i>	Research and Innovation Action
<i>Eligibility conditions</i>	The proposal must apply the multi-actor approach.

Successful proposals will contribute to the following outcomes:

- Increased evidence of the environmental benefits of minor crops;
- Farmers make use of a wider range of crops, and combination of crops;
- Minor crops are integrated in farming systems promoting their environmental benefits;
- Increased resilience and climate adaptation of farming systems vis-a-vis biotic/abiotic stress;
- Feed and food industry make use of minor crops;
- Creation of new avenues for farmers and value chains through a wider range of products.

Scope:

Farmers face increasing pressure to shift production towards lower input systems, while continuing to ensure sufficient supplies of food and non-food products. Activities shall release the value of minor crops and promote their broader use in breeding, farming and in food/non-food value chains. For the purpose of this topic, minor crops are defined as underutilised crops.

- Promote the access to minor crops engaging in breeding activities
- Improve agronomic management practices for minor crops

Explore the effects and benefits of minor crops and demonstrate the ecosystems services supported by farming system diversification and the integration of minor crops (if applicable, including novel crop rotations).

- Identify and test avenues for marketing and processing of more diverse farming outputs across the value chain;
- Promote the uptake of minor crops through the development of guidelines and wide-spread practical demonstrations taking into account a range of farming systems, pedo-climatic conditions and value chains;
- Support capacity building, training and education enabling farmers/growers to adopt sustainable agricultural practices.

Activities must implement the **multi-actor approach**, thus ensure an adequate involvement of researchers, farmers, advisors, food industry, and other players in the value chain and consumers. Communication and outreach to a wide range of stakeholders is essential.

¹ Minor Crops: Diverse Nutzpflanzen (zB Kräuter, Gemüse, Beerenobst), die einen vergleichsweise hohen Marktwert haben, in begrenzten Gebieten angebaut werden und für die vergleichsweise wenig Pflanzenschutzmittel zugelassen sind.

A more detailed description of the four characters

Character	Interests/Objectives/Red lines	Complementarities with others	Possible Conflicts
Bo Hansen: Professor in Plant Production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experience in EU research projects, but no experience with MA • Needs to set up scientifically sound experiments and write scientific papers • Interests lies in the breeding of minor crops and exploring the possibilities of hybrid or genetically modified plants, focused on increasing the resistance of the plants against pests. • RED LINE: Scientific papers and experiments are a must. Otherwise, the scientist cannot commit. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With the Sensor SME: The scientist sees an added value of using sensors in his experiments as this would increase the scientific value and accuracy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With the Advisory Organisation: The scientist wants to focus on experiments related to breeding plants resistant to pests using genome editing techniques. The Advisory Organisation's red line is that this is not the sole focus of the project.
Lucca Gold: Team leader of an organic farming advisory organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involved in EU-funded MA project before • Needs extra inputs to provide better advice to their farmers – interested in having clear guidelines how they can help their farmers benefit from the use of minor crops on their farm and how they can change their agronomic management practices. • Interests lies in the environmental benefits the use of minor crops can create and want to focus on how different minor crops can complement each other in cultivation practices and diversification strategies on the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With the Producer Group: They see added value in better understanding the market opportunities of minor crops in order to integrate this in their advisory services + a connection to farmers willing to implement experiments • With the Sensor SME: Using sensors could reduce the use of harmful chemical fertilisers and pesticides. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With the Scientist: The advisory service also wants on-farm experiments related to agronomic management practices vs. the Scientist who wants lab-based experiments only.

Character	Interests/Objectives/Red lines	Complementarities with others	Possible Conflicts
	<p>farm. They would like to include on-farm experiments on agronomic management practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RED LINE: If the use of gene editing in the breeding is too explicit in the proposal, their organisation cannot commit. 		
Danni Winter: Board member/Director of a Producer Group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involved in EU-funded MA project before • Needs better insights into how minor crops can create added value for their members/farmers and is interested in support in the development of the value chain. • Interests lie in the market opportunity created by these minor crops and how they can further develop the activities within the Erzeugergemeinschaft including processing • RED LINE: If the needs of their members are disregarded and none of the experiments can be done on-farm or at their premises. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With the Scientist: They see benefits in direct access to better breeding techniques using genome editing. • With the advisory organisation: Having their members involved in on-farm experiments will reflect well on their organisation. Combining the on-farm experiments with their own experiments on processing and marketing the crops will help them in developing the value chain using project funds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With the Scientist: They would like to also have the voices of their members heard in which types of experiments and minor crops the scientist will work. The scientist does not think this is scientifically sound. • With the Sensor SME: This type of technology is too expensive for their members. The value chain development should come first.
Lumen Solinse: Sensor technology SME	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No experience in EU-funded projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With the Scientist: Having the scientist use their technology in their experiments, would allow them to further 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With the Scientist: They are unsure whether they want to share certain details related to their technology with

Character	Interests/Objectives/Red lines	Complementarities with others	Possible Conflicts
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Needs more elaborate testing of the sensors they developed that help with the rapid detection of different types of pests • Interests lies with making their sensor technology competitive and ready for the market. Therefore they are interested in a close connection with farmers and would like their sensors to be part of the practical demonstrations and the training kits. • RED LINE: They do not want to fully disclose the ins-and outs of their technology development process and aim at a patent application at the end of the project. 	<p>finetune it in a scientifically sound setting.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With the Advisory organisation: They see a market opportunity in having the Advisory organisation as a fan of their sensor technology. It would be interesting if the advisory services include the potential of their technology in their advice. • With the Producer Group: Direct access to farmers and how they would use their technology would provide very interesting information to make their sensors competitive. 	<p>the scientist and do not want to share the patent with the scientist.</p>

Poster templates Round 1: one per character, A1 size

Professor Bo Hanse

Professor Hanse is a plant scientist at a renowned University

- ▶ Previous experience working in EU research projects
- ▶ Superficial understanding of the 'Multi-actor approach'
- ▶ Scientific paper writing and publishing
- ▶ Fields of expertise:
 - ▶ (Hybrid) breeding including GMOs
 - ▶ Improving quality at harvest, during storage and transport

INTERESTS & OBJECTIVES

RED LINES

ACTIVITIES

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Lucca Gold

Lucca Gold is the team leader of an advisory service specialised in organic farming

- ▶ A lot of experience in EU multi-actor projects
- ▶ Information to support farm advisory services on the cultivation of minor crops
- ▶ On-farm research
- ▶ Fields of expertise:
 - ▶ Conversion from conventional to organic farming
 - ▶ Agro-biodiversity

INTERESTS & OBJECTIVES

RED LINES

ACTIVITIES

Funded by the European Union | Ghent University for Sustainable Development | ILVO | PREMIERE

Lumen Solinse

Lumen Solinse is the CEO of a successful start-up SME in sensor technology development and distribution

- ▶ No experience working in EU or multi-actor projects
- ▶ New sensor technology needs testing
- ▶ Reliable detection of pests and proof of origin for marketing
- ▶ Sensor technology which is technically superior than the competitors
- ▶ On-farm testing of sensors

INTERESTS & OBJECTIVES

RED LINES

ACTIVITIES

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Danni Winter

Danni Winter is a board member of a Producer Organisation

Experience with multi-actor projects, but not with EU projects

- ▶ Build niche value chains for members
- ▶ Field trials should involve member farms
- ▶ Increase profit
- ▶ Fields of expertise:
 - ▶ Knowledge on transport, storage and packaging
 - ▶ Value chain development

INTERESTS & OBJECTIVES

RED LINES

ACTIVITIES

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Poster template Round 2: One per mixed group, A0 size

Poster template Round 3: one per mixed group, A0 size

Designing the project: Developing Work Packages

- ▶ You need to find a coordinator amongst yourselves
- ▶ You first ideas for 3 Work Packages (WP) in this project, for each WP you define a theme or a group of activities and who will be (not) involved in this WP from the group of partners already around the table.
- ▶ Which additional partners would you still need to successfully implement your project?

Original ideas for activities

Project Coordinator

WP 1		
WHO?		WHAT?
Missing?		

		WP 2
WHO?		WHAT?
Missing?		

WP 3		
WHO?		WHAT?
Missing?		